

Customer Segmentation Using Machine Learning for Targeted Marketing: A Study on Bangladeshi Consumers

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Abstract:

Purpose: This research explores the efficiency of machine learning approaches for customer segmentation in the e-commerce sector of Bangladesh. The aim is to understand the role of segmentation in targeted marketing strategies while identifying the determinant behavioural, psychographic and demographic factors influencing the segmentation.

Design/methodology/approach: A quantitative research design was adopted using secondary data methods and algorithms such as K-means clustering, Decision Tree, and Random Forest. These analytical approaches were used to isolate and identify distinctive user groups and assess key predictive variables. In addition, VADER was used for polarity scoring and numeric emotion mapping which led the lexicon-based sentiment and emotional analyses. This approach is expected to enhance psychographic insights across product categories and platforms.

Findings: The study has identified four customer segments with distinct behavioural patterns, the most significant predictive features being total spend, membership status and average product ratings. Behavioural and psychographic variables provided an in-depth understanding of segmentation than traditional demographic variables. Psychological dimension was added to the study through emotion and sentiment scoring, revealing emotionally engaged customer groups. In emerging markets like Bangladesh, these findings can offer helpful guidance for data-driven targeting, engagement and retention strategies.

Originality/value: This research generates actionable marketing insights through providing an integrated ML-based segmentation approach combining behavioural, transactional and emotional data. Results complement the existing literature and implores the underexplored Bangladeshi e-commerce market by applying these techniques and demonstrates how data-driven segmentation can be used to improve personalisation, loyalty and retention strategies.

Keywords: Customer Segmentation, Machine Learning, K-Means Clustering, Random Forest, Sentiment Analysis, Psychographics, E-commerce, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

1.1 Background

In today's data-driven business world, customer behaviour holds an essential role in planning effective marketing strategies. Segmenting a company's customer data following characteristic patterns allows companies to target and improve their marketing campaigns to achieve higher customer satisfaction and loyalty. Traditional methods of segmentation involving demographic, behavioural and geographic categories such as age, gender, purchasing patterns and location no longer accurately reflect the complicated behavioural and psychographic characteristics of modern consumer preferences (Wang, 2024). Therefore, segmentation involving retailer knowledge and available data may not provide a comprehensive understanding of customer requirements.

Widely used big data and data mining techniques like machine learning (ML) have revolutionised customer segmentation which requires large datasets to identify hidden relationships and patterns. K-means clustering and other algorithms can accelerate customer data analysis by segmenting customers into groups with similar characteristics to maximise the efficacy of future marketing campaigns for specific customer groups (Bogacki et al., 2024). Particular models, i.e., Logistic Regression, Decision Trees, Random Forests, AdaBoost and Gaussian Mixture Models offer distinct advantages and trade-offs in terms of segmentation quality and interpretability (Madhiraju et al., 2024).

Studies indicate that Customer segmentation in Bangladesh is evolving rapidly, catalysed by the country's fast-changing socioeconomic, cultural and technological landscapes (Aziz et al., 2023). The increased growth of middle income citizens has accompanied by continued growth in the economy which has been facilitated by the processes of urbanisation and digitalisation of consumption patterns (Shebalov, 2015). Regardless of these changes, traditional segmentation approaches are still widely used in Bangladesh which often fail to recognise and detect these intrinsic factors (Zimon et al., 2020). This study aims to explore the potential of ML-based customer segmentation to stipulate better informed and insights into targeted marketing in Bangladesh.

1.2 Problem Statement

Many businesses depend on traditional segmentation methods that mainly focus on demographic factors even though consumer data is becoming more available in Bangladesh (Rahman et al., 2024). This strategy overlooks the intricacies of the behavioural and psychographic aspects of modern consumer behaviour. These methods will affect the marketing; it will bring generic strategies, poorly targeted campaigns and increased customer acquisition costs. The lack of standardisation in segmentation methods

used by studies complicates the comparison of results and identifies the most productive practices (Ijegwa David Acheme & Esosa Enoyoze, 2024).

Recent research by Ali et al (2023) highlights that most empirical studies have used demographic data. And it does not take into account important behavioural and psychographic factors that provide useful insights into consumer choice and desire. In existing research, the lack of awareness of the cultural nuances leads to generalised conclusions that might not be practical in diverse markets like Bangladesh (Ho et al., 2023). The dependency on static segmentation models might make these issues worse as they do not adjust to the changing consumer behaviour over time.

There is a significant research gap in the use of ML-based segmentation techniques, mainly in the Bangladeshi market. In dynamic and culturally sensitive segmentation, ML has not been fully utilised despite the promise of large volumes of data and hidden patterns that it can identify (Lathifah & Azzahra, 2025). It is essential to find a solution to this gap because ML-based segmentation would allow businesses to create more customised marketing campaigns that respond to the evolving preferences of consumers and enhance their customer involvement and competitive advantages.

1.3 Research Objective & Gap

The primary objectives of this research are to apply and compare machine learning algorithms with traditional methods for customer segmentation using Bangladeshi consumer data and to identify and evaluate key behavioural, psychographic and demographic factors that influence effective customer segmentation in Bangladesh. Additionally, assess the impact of ML-based segmentation on targeted marketing outcomes.

Although ML-based customer segmentation has been extensively studied in global contexts, limited research is available on its use in the Bangladesh market. Segmentation methods that rely on traditional demographics techniques are missing from existing studies, as they fail to acknowledge the complexity of modern consumer behaviour and psychographic characteristics (Loh Rahim et al., 2018). As the marketing field operates predominantly on a data-agnostic basis, no standardised methodologies exist for studies in this area which prevents the development of actionable marketing strategies. This study aims to address these gaps by using advanced ML models to reveal ever-changing and culturally significant segments of customers, leading to targeted marketing within Bangladesh.

This study contributes to both academic knowledge and industry practices in multiple ways. By using ML techniques for customer segmentation and sentiment analysis, Bangladeshi companies can develop more personalised and accurate marketing strategies which lead to improved customer engagement, higher

conversion rates and reduced marketing expenses. This paper discusses the use of customer clustering techniques based on review behaviour and purchasing behaviour. It allows businesses to identify key segments and develop targeted plans. It also uses sentiment and emotion analysis of online product reviews to find the emotional tones and degree of customer satisfaction. Those insights are supposed to support personalisation and help companies to effectively address customer needs. This research gap that the study addresses is related to the use of advanced ML techniques in the Bangladeshi market where the market is rapidly digitalising and has a change in consumer behaviour at the same time.

This paper is structured and a review of suitable literature on customer segmentation, machine learning applications and targeted marketing is presented (Section 2). Then, Section 3 describes the methodology including the sample, data collection, analytical techniques and ethical considerations. Section 4 presents the results which are compared with similar studies, and their implications for Bangladeshi consumer marketing are discussed. Finally, Section 5 presents conclusions, theoretical and practical contributions, limitations and directions for future research.

2. Literature Review

The core strategy the modern marketing industry employs is segmentation, which involves stratifying the client population based on shared characteristics and needs. This allows businesses to focus on their marketing strategies to meet specific consumer preferences, increasing both customer satisfaction and business performance (Ijegwa David Acheme et al. 2024).

Segmentation has become important and is enabled by the availability of data and accurate analytical tools. Evaluation of the demographic, behavioural and psychographic data leads the organisations to build stronger consumer bonds and improve brand loyalty (Loh Rahim et al., 2018). Also, Kaur et al (2023) highlight that it has served the business well in terms of distributing marketing resources that improve their return on investment by targeting promising customers. The ML method k-means clustering has improved the effectiveness of segmentation by analysing large datasets to uncover complex patterns in customer behaviour (Hirve et al, 2024). Importantly, segmentation allows businesses to adjust marketing techniques as per customer preferences and market conditions (Shebalov, 2015).

Four conventional market segments usually emerge based on demographic and geographic factors, psychographic and behavioural characteristics (Amin, 2024). These are the most commonly used segmentation methods across both developed and developing countries, including Bangladesh (Rashid et al., 2009). Demographic segmentation categorises consumers according to their age, gender, income,

education, occupation and family size. To exemplify, Bangladeshi telecom companies like Grameenphone and Robi design to target students, professionals and rural users using demographic data (Baki et al. 2018). Geographic segmentation tends to divide consumers based on location. The available products and delivery services offered by e-commerce platforms like Daraz and Chaldal are different in Dhaka city compared to smaller towns (Jamal, 2016). Psychographic segmentation reforms consumer segments by considering lifestyle, values and personality traits. Digital brands in Bangladesh are mainly targeting sustainable products that cater to environmentally conscious consumers (Amin et al. 2024). On the other hand, behavioural segmentation identifies consumers based on their purchase and engagement behaviours. Platforms employing this approach to provide personalise rewards, had attained better customer retention rate such as Nagad and bKash (Rahman et al., 2024). Studies have noted a significant improvement in targeting accuracy where traditional segmentation was integrated with digital and behavioural data (Akinrinoye et al., 2020).

Nonetheless, recent consumer behaviour shifts are not well represented in the traditional segmented customer analysis following the demographic data (Ali et al., 2023). According to Wedel and Kannan, machine learning is more adaptive and precise in providing segmentation through real time analysis of various data such as demographic, transactional and behavioural information (Wedel & Kannan, 2016). The predictive model helps the firms to identify customer turnover patterns revealing strategic marketing opportunities (Amutha & Khan, 2023). ML technologies facilitate increase in customer loyalty and allows businesses to compete highly saturated markets (Kiran & Ashwini, 2024). One of the most significant breakthroughs in customer engagement and retention management is the development of a dynamic segmentation system (Reddy et al., 2021). The method identifies overlooked behavioural sequences and psychological motivators and leads to advanced, accurate and active segmentation (Janaki et al., 2024). Real-time profile updates ensure that businesses can continually identify marketing opportunities (Kasem et al., 2023). Consequently, Bangladesh's e-commerce and digital finance industries strongly benefit from ML techniques by improving customer engagement and retention. Such algorithms have become integral to detecting meaningful behavioral patterns and driving personalised marketing strategies (Akinrinoye et al., 2020).

Clustering algorithms are unsupervised learning models that classify customers into clusters with similar characteristics. K-means clustering divides into 'k' clusters by minimising variance within each group (Datta et al., 2024). Although it is suitable for large datasets, but less effective with clusters of different sizes or non-spherical shapes (Wani et al. 2023). Gaussian Mixture Models (GMM) address these limitations by providing the advantage of being flexible with a probability and can have a partial membership of clusters, making them a superior model for complex datasets (Mark, 2023). Ensemble

techniques apply various models to enhance the stability and accuracy of predictions in customer segmentation and targeted marketing (Lessmann et al. 2021). Models applied following ensemble techniques and based on Decision Trees can generate interpretable rules that are able to forecast outcomes like purchase likelihood or churn risk (Gankidi et al. 2022).

Individual decision trees with complicated datasets, despite their intuitive nature, are prone to overfitting, as shown in a recent work by Loganathan and Reddy (2024). Copious number of decision trees with random sub-datasets and combined outputs are generated by random forests to overcome these limitations. This strategy is known to reduce overfitting, increase robustness and provide better generalisation which proves to be a superior technique for predicting customer lifetime value, upselling opportunities or customer retention patterns (Nagaraj et al., 2023). Extreme Gradient Boosting (XGBoost) integrates regularisation and is effective with missing data (Gankidi et al., 2022). Comprehensive tools provided by these clustering and ensemble methods allows companies to reveal relevant customer insights through ensuring accurate segmentation and impactful marketing campaigns (Olalekan Hamed Olayinka, 2021). Segmentation insights are essential in identifying market gaps and guiding development of new products. Detection of at-risk customers through targeted offer can assist the companies to reduce churn and promote customer re-engagement (Nagaraj et al., 2023). ML segmentation is crucial for pricing strategy and revenue maximisation all while retaining market competitiveness (Reddy et al. 2021).

Advanced segmentation is adopted in industry leading companies by implementing machine learning techniques. To exemplify, Amazon adopted K-means and collaborative filtering to cluster customers by their purchase patterns, browsing and preferences, boosting the accuracy of recommendations. Walmart employs similar models to predict shopping patterns (Lathifah & Azzahra, 2025). American Express uses predictive modelling and decision trees to sort the cardholders based on their spending practices. In Bangladesh, popular e-commerce vendors like Daraz and Chaldal use K-means clustering to cluster consumers by their product preferences and purchase behaviours (Amin, 2024). Financial services like bKash categorise users based on digital engagement data, while banks such as Dutch-Bangla Bank use predictive algorithms to evaluate risks and customise credit services (Das, 2024). Location data and order behaviour are two factors widely used by online service providers such as Foodpanda and Pathao to optimise promotions (Badruddozza, 2021). Grameenphone also rely on its customer data usage and call pattern information to offer specific incentives and data packages to customers based on their needs (Lathifah & Azzahra, 2025). These applications have improved conversion and retention, which emphasises the importance of data quality and feature engineering to be effective in segmentation (Rahman et al., 2024). As adoption grows, machine learning will spearhead more personalised and efficient marketing strategies in Bangladesh.

Customer segmentation has been a critical component of marketing strategy (Madhiraju et al., 2024). However, the development of digital platforms exposed the limitations of traditional segmentation methods and led to a growing interest in ML as a dynamic and data-driven strategy (Theodorakopoulos et al. 2024). Studies have demonstrated the success of ML methods, particularly unsupervised clustering-based strategies, such as k-means and hierarchical clustering algorithms, in revealing natural customer groups (Mahnoor et al., 2024; Wang, 2024). Predictive algorithms enable to identification of high-value customers, while clustering models and classification algorithms such as random forests improve customer profile accuracy (Bogacki et al, 2024). ML models also improve personalisation and customer engagement compared to rule-based systems (Madhiraju et al, 2024). Some studies now incorporate natural language processing (NLP) into segmentation models to analyse reviews and feedback, adding emotional context. However, this aspect has not been sufficiently developed, mainly in the context of emerging economies like Bangladesh, where the pace of digitalisation is expected to continue to increase (Arif et al. 2021).

The association between customer data input techniques and marketing outcomes is highlighted in this study framework through segmentation analysis using ML techniques. This research explores several customer variables of Bangladeshi consumers such as demographic, psychographic and behavioural data while using clustering and ensemble procedures to find significant segments. This framework integrates traditional models with data-driven techniques such as K-means clustering, decision trees, random forests and Lexicon-based sentiment and emotion. This two-track approach enables us to generate both behavioural and emotional baselines allowing a more comprehensive understating of customer segmentation. The resulting system is designed to generate customised marketing strategies aimed at improving consumer engagement, customisation and retention.

3. Methodology

This chapter outlines the research methodologies we have adopted in this study to explore the efficiency of machine learning techniques in customer segmentation. As stated previously, this research perimeter is specified to Bangladeshi e-commerce market only. It provides an overview of the study's purpose, research design, data sources, sampling methods and statistical techniques employed in the analysis. The research purpose directs and helps shaping study activities, defining the research objectives and supporting the design.

3.1 Sample and Data Collection

The primary demographic, psychographic and behavioural characteristics are identified in this study using a descriptive methodology which grouped using machine learning techniques. A quantitative research framework is followed to maintain consistency with research objectives and data availability. According to Bhagat and Bakariya (2025), this design allows researchers to cross-check the results using multiple methods which helps in improving depth and accuracy of the study.

This work draws from existing open-access e-commerce review datasets hosted on Kaggle, a source that track customer activity across major digital shopping platforms in Bangladesh, such as Daraz and Ajkerdeal. Consumer information such as behavioural, demographic and transactional data is covered within these datasets whereas analysis contains transaction logs, user-submitted product reviews, browsing activity, consumer ratings etc. This study explores non-probability sampling following the nature and characteristics of the data. However, sampling is entirely reliant on available user records since researchers have no authority over random selections.

The dataset contains more than 10,000 records consisting structured behavioural and transactional data alongside thousands of unstructured product reviews. Such a dataset is reliable and provides strong foundation for using K-means clustering for unsupervised segmentation and Random Forest and Decision Tree classifier for predictive modelling. Being large scale, approaches such as splitting data into training and testing parts work more effectively, improving how well findings apply to Bangladeshi online shoppers. Furthermore, assessing model accuracy benefits from repeated testing through cross-validation and standard holdout strategies.

For this research, variables were grouped into three categories as followed – demographic, behavioural and psychographic category. Demographics are denoted through age and gender data whereas total expenditure, purchase history, membership status, usage and recency cover the behavioural variables by accounting for consumer activity on the platform. Satisfaction levels, feedback ratings and written comments shaped the psychological traits, drawn from personal responses. For ensure equal importance during clustering and predictive modelling, variables were standardised using a z-score transformation. Feature selection was guided by domain knowledge and exploratory data analysis to ensure relevance. Sentiment and emotion variables were derived by natural language processing techniques. And review polarity was determined based on the VADER lexicon, while emotional intensity was mapped to numeric scores. The text preprocessing involved lowercasing, punctuation removal, stopword filtering and lemmatisation.

3.2 Techniques for Analysis

The analysis was conducted using ML methods on both structured customer data and unstructured review texts. Such techniques were divided into two analytical tracks. In Track 1, K-Means Clustering was used to identify natural segments of the behavioural dataset. The elbow method was used to identify the optimal number of clusters. K-means is effective for large datasets and performs well on numeric behavioural variables after standardisation (Ho et al., 2023). Other algorithms like Hierarchical Clustering or DBSCAN are less suitable as they are computationally expensive for large datasets and struggle with high-dimensional data (Wang, 2024). Decision Tree & Random Forest Classification models validated clustering results and also examined the influence of different features on cluster membership. Instead of other models (e.g, SVM or Logistic Regression), Random Forest was used as it has the ability to handle nonlinear patterns, reduce overfitting and it gives clear feature importance scores which are relevant for interpretation (Reddy et al., 2021).

In Track 2, sentiment and emotion analyses used lexicon-based NLP techniques. VADER sentiment scoring assigned polarity scores to reviews which enabling sentiment analysis across products and platforms (Olalekan Hamed Olayinka, 2021). As the texts in reviews were mostly written in Bengali, VADER was used without changing the lexicon after cleaning the text. The approach was adopted as many Bengali opinion words (e.g., ভালো, খারাপ, অসাধারণ, বাজে) have explicit positive or negative polarity which allows the Vader rule-based system to identify common sentiment patterns. Furthermore, some specific features like repeated characters, punctuation intensity and long expressions commonly seen in Bangladeshi online reviews were retained and allowed VADER to use its advantage in processing expressive user-generated text (Hutto and Gilbert, 2014). Emotional intensity mapping measured emotional tones by transforming labels into weighted numerical scores used in psychographic analysis.

All analyses were performed in Python, leveraging libraries such as Scikit-learn, Pandas, Seaborn, Matplotlib, and NLTK. The data preprocessing steps ensured that the input was cleaned, scaled, and formatted correctly for each model type.

3.3 Ethical Considerations

Since the study used secondary data, it ensures all datasets are publicly available and anonymised and free from personally identifiable information. Data processing was conducted with privacy and data confidentiality standards aligned with institutional ethical guidelines. Each dataset was checked to confirm compliance with data protection standards and the absence of sensitive or private information.

The purpose is purely academic and seeks to enhance understanding of customer segmentation through machine learning. Results are presented at a massive level to prevent the identification of individual participants or records.

4. Results

This chapter demonstrates the findings derived from applying ML techniques to customer behaviour and reviewing data from the Bangladeshi e-commerce market. The analysis was structured into two tracks. Track 1 Applied unsupervised and supervised machine learning algorithms (K-means clustering, Decision Tree, Random Forest) to structured consumer behaviour data to detect customer segments and the most significant variables that explain customer behaviour. Track 2 applied sentiment and emotion analysis on consumer-generated product reviews based on lexicon-based models and weighted intensity scoring to provide psychographic understanding of customer responses.

4.1 Track 1 – Customer Segmentation Using Machine Learning

The customer behaviour dataset includes a set of demographic, behavioural, and transactional features. These were standardised to z-scores to cluster efficiently. Nine variables, like Gender, Age, Total Spend, Number of Items Purchased, Average Product Rating, Satisfaction Score, Discount Used, Days Since Last Purchase, and Membership Status, were chosen for segmentation. The Elbow Method was used in determining the optimal number of clusters (k), which is four. The K-means algorithm identified four distinct segments as shown in Figure 4.1.

Cluster 0 shows the lowest values across most variables, including total spend (-1.10), items purchased (-1.21), satisfaction (-1.28) and membership (-1.23), which represent low-value, disengaged customers.

Cluster 1 records moderately positive scores for total spend (+0.72) and items purchased (+0.73), and slightly above-average satisfaction (+0.36). These customers are moderately engaged, younger customers with loyalty potential. Cluster 2 is characterised by high satisfaction (+1.23) and relatively high discount usage(+0.93), but low spend (-0.96) and purchase volume (-0.73). These are older, discount-driven, but satisfied buyers. Cluster 3 shows low satisfaction (-1.11), purchase frequency (-0.22), and discount use (-1.00), despite positive membership status (+1.27), which represents Disengaged members maintaining membership but low engagement and purchase activity.

Table 4.1: Summary of Customer Clusters by Spend and Engagement

Cluster	Spend (Std)	Items	Satisfaction	Description
0	-1.10	-1.21	-1.28	Low-Value Disengaged
1	0.72	0.73	0.36	Moderate Users
2	-0.96	-0.73	1.23	Discount-Driven Satisfied Buyers
3	-0.22	-0.22	-1.11	lapsed Members

These findings show how behavioural clustering using machine learning provides richer insights than demographic ones, aligning with (Kaur et al., 2023; Wedel & Kannan, 2016), who observed that ML-based segmentation increases targeting accuracy and engagement.

Figure 4.2: Random Forest Feature Importance Plot

Supervised learning was applied using a random forest model trained on the same dataset for validate these clusters. As seen in Figure 4.2, age was the strongest predictor of cluster membership (importance score 0.34), followed by membership status (0.14), total spend (0.12) and satisfaction (0.12). Less powerful factors were average rating (0.08), items purchased (0.07), discount usage (0.06), recency (0.04)

and gender (0.01). These results confirm that behavioural and psychographic indicators are much better predictors than demographic ones (Bhagat & Bakariya, 2025).

Figure 4.3: Model Accuracy Comparison Bar Chart

Table 4.2: ML Models Compared by Performance and Insight

Model	Type	Accuracy (Train Set)	Accuracy (Test Set)	CV Score (5-Fold)	Use Case
K-Means	Unsupervised	–	–	–	Discover clusters
Decision Tree	Supervised	1.00	0.99	0.99	Explain segmentation rules
Random Forest	Supervised	1.00	1.00	0.99	Rank features for prediction

The Decision Tree and Random Forest models were compared using a 70/30 train-test split with 5-fold cross-validation. (Figure 4.3). The Decision Tree had a high accuracy rate (0.99) on test data, but it had weak overfitting, while the Random Forest had a high accuracy rate (1.00) on both training and testing, with a 0.99 cross-validation score, which validates its strengths. Random Forest’s ensemble approach was more stable and more interpretable, and it can be used in scalable customer segmentation for marketing applications. (Figure 4.3; Table 4.2). Compared to traditional segmentation, the ML approach showed deeper behavioural distinctions with more practical marketing implications. (Table 4.3).

Table 4.3: Comparison of Traditional vs. ML-Based Segmentation

Method	Features Used	Actionability	Depth of Insight
Traditional	Age, Gender	Low	Basic grouping
ML-Based	Behaviour, Satisfaction	High	Nuanced clusters

4.2 Track 2: Sentiment and Emotion Analysis of Product Reviews

The review dataset comprises textual and categorical data from customer reviews including review text, product category, platform, and star ratings. Two psychographic metrics were extracted using lexicon-based NLP. Sentiment Scores were derived using the VADER SentimentIntensityAnalyzer which assigns a compound polarity score ranging from -1 to +1 based on the emotional tone of the review text. Given that a significant part of the reviews was composed in Bengali, the analysis incorporated the text-cleaning processes which preserved polarity-carrying words in Bengali and such features of the text as repetition and punctuations. And for Emotion Score, Emotion labels (e.g., Love, Angry, Neutral) were mapped to numeric values on a scale of +2 to -2 to capture the emotional intensity and direction.

Figure 4.4: Bar Chart of Sentiment by Product Category

The sentiment scores had distinct categorical differences. The highest sentiment score was shown in Phone accessories (0.158) which is significantly above the overall mean sentiment score of approximately 0.07. An average score was achieved by home essentials and electronics (~0.085). And fashion, grocery and kids & baby products also had a medium score (~0.050-0.065). Conversely, the office supplies, beauty, and home care products had positive sentiment scores (~0.005- 0.02). These results indicate that positive sentiment was associated with lifestyle-based categories (Figure 4.4).

Figure 4.5: Emotion Score by Product Category

A similar trend was observed in Emotion intensity (Figure 4.5). Phone accessories had the highest mean emotion score (0.45) which is noticeably higher than the overall average of approximately 0.27. Home essentials (0.34) and kids & baby (0.31) also recorded average emotional intensity that indicates strong responses from customers. The home care(0.21), office supplies(0.20) and beauty (0.19) showed lower results which reflect more natural customer perceptions.

Figure 4.6: Sentiment & Emotion by Customer Segment

Sentiment and emotion scores also varied across the four customer segments (Figure 4.6). Segment 0 exhibits a moderately low sentiment of 0.28 and a high emotion intensity of 0.51 which implies that the customers have emotional expressions. Segment 1 shows the lowest sentiment (0.24) and a relatively lower emotion (0.46) which indicates weaker emotional involvement and more neutral feedback. Segment 2 has the highest sentiment of roughly 0.30 and the strong emotional intensity (~0.56) as it contains highly expressive customers who can be characterised by strong affective responses. Segment 3

demonstrates an average level of sentiment (~ 0.27) and a relatively high level of emotion (~ 0.50) which indicates that the individual experiences stable emotional interaction even with inconsistent behavioural patterns.

Figure 4.7: Correlation Heatmap of Rating, Sentiment, and Emotion

A correlation analysis was executed to assess the relationships between star ratings, sentiment polarity and emotional intensity. As shown, the sentiment and emotion scores have a very strong positive correlation ($r = +0.98$). And the correlation of rating and sentiment was at $+0.77$, rating and emotion were also positive (0.76) which verifies that the emotional tone is associated with sentiment polarity and satisfaction (Figure 4.6).

Figure 4.8: Sentiment Distribution by Review Source

Sentiment analysis by platform (Figure 4.7) showed Daraz received the highest number of reviews, which included approximately 1800 positive and 1600 negative reviews, making the total number of reviews nearly 3400. AjkeDeal had approximately 800 positive and 725 negative reviews, adding up to approximately 1525 reviews. The sentiment on both platforms was positive, yet Daraz maintained higher, which could be due to greater trust and quality of services.

4.3 Actionable Insights and Marketing Recommendations

Segment / Insight	Marketing Strategy
Low-Value Disengaged	Reactivation campaigns and personalised outreach
Moderate Users	Loyalty programs and targeted recommendations
Discount-Driven Satisfied Buyers	Flash sales and coupon-based promotions
Lapsed Members	Service recovery and exclusive member offers

The segmentation and sentiment analysis ensure that marketing strategic decisions can be made effectively. The customer cluster and emotion can be incorporated in a corresponding marketing strategy to maximise management, retention and conversion (Theodorakopoulos & Theodoropoulou, 2024; Tan, 2024).

4.4 Interpretation of Findings

This study explored how ML techniques can improve customer segmentation for target marketing in Bangladesh. The findings are consistent with previous works like Wedel and Kannan (2016) which highlighted that Machine Learning is more accurate compared to traditional demographics.

The identified segments have academic and managerial implications. The moderately high spending, high purchase frequency and above-average satisfaction indicate the customers with strong potential to become high-value, loyal buyers. Those customers should be targeted through relationship-building strategies like loyalty rewards, exclusive product previews or early access to promotions. Another group exhibited low spending (-1.10), very low purchase frequency (-1.21), and the lowest satisfaction (-1.28). They should be prioritised for reactivation via personalised communication.

Random Forest and Decision Tree models proved that behavioural and transactional variables contributed to successful deep segmentation. Specifically, the Random Forest algorithm emphasised age (34%), membership status (14%), total spend (12%) and satisfaction score (12%) echoes the work of Hirve et al. (2024) and Lathifah and Azzahra (2025), who also found that behavioural data has more richer segmentation base than demographic characteristics. Gender had very limited predictive power (1%), reaffirming that demographic variables alone are insufficient in modern segmentations, which is also supported by Ali et al. (2023). The accuracy of the model indicates the strength, highlighting the

superiority of the behavioural segmentation, especially in Bangladesh's rapidly digitalising markets (Ali et al., 2023; Hirve et al., 2024).

Further depth was added through sentiment and emotion analyses of customer reviews. The higher emotional engagement in products with lifestyle-oriented reflects Singh et al. (2024), who linked emotion-oriented purchase behaviour with more customer loyalty. Product categories such as phone accessories showed the highest average sentiment score (~ 0.158), indicating that customers were very satisfied and had positive experiences with the product. Also, phone accessories (~ 0.45), home essentials (~ 0.34), and kids and baby (~ 0.31) products were the most emotionally intense purchases. These categories make them well-suited to marketing strategies such as stories, influencer marketing and brand communication. Utilitarian categories, home care (~ 0.005 sentiment, ~ 0.21 emotion), office supplies (~ 0.02 sentiment, ~ 0.20 emotion) and beauty (~ 0.015 sentiment, ~ 0.19 emotion) were lower sentiment and emotional scores which suggests more neutral or functional product perceptions.

There were positive correlations in numeric ratings, sentiment, and emotion which further elucidated the pattern of consumer perception. The sentiment and emotion scores were very strong ($r = 0.98$) that indicates the emotional tone correlates well with sentiment polarity. The fact that the correlation between sentiment and rating is strong ($r = 0.77$) affirms the findings by Madhiraju et al. (2024), as they found sentiment is a positive text and it is associated with high rating scores and purchase intention.

Sentiment and emotion patterns with segments provide an insightful understanding of customer behaviour than transactional characteristics. A low sentiment (~ 0.28) and high emotion intensity (~ 0.51) are observed in Segment 0 which is associated with low spending and weak engagement and that indicates frustration or dissatisfaction by disengaged customers despite low engagement. Segment 1 which includes moderate users with constant activity, showed a low emotional expression (~ 0.46) which reflects more functional and neutral feedback. In contrast, the highest sentiment (~ 0.30) and emotion intensity of approximately 0.56 are found in segment 2, the satisfied and discount-driven customers, which makes them especially open to value-driven communication. Segment 3 (lapsed members) has moderate sentiment (~ 0.27) with a strong emotional tone (~ 0.50) that demonstrates dissatisfaction despite prolonged membership. These patterns indicate satisfied and engaged groups (Segment 2) tend to exhibit greater emotional expression than low-value and disengaged groups (Segment 0), thereby differentiating between the behavioural drivers of each group (Wedel & Kannan, 2016).

However, the correlation between rating and emotion ($r = 0.76$) indicates that customer emotion may align with overall satisfaction but may vary depending on the product context. This correlation shows the

importance of capturing emotions that convey modest aspects of perceived consumer perceptions that ratings can not express. The platforms cannot be based solely to average rating scores; they also should integrate tactical and emotional indicators to obtain comprehensive understanding of customer experience and brand sentiment (Arif et al., 2021)

Also, the dominance positive sentiment Daraz exhibits over AjkerDeal supports the findings of Amin (2024) that reliable platforms significantly predict consumer trust and satisfaction. These distinctions indicate that it has higher consumer protection, performance, and perception of services, whereas AjkerDeal may face problems with delivery consistency or user-friendliness. This highlights that product perception is particularly limited by platform infrastructure and customer service, which are often underestimated within a strictly product-centred strategy (Kumar & Reinartz, 2016).

The optimal target audience of loyalty improvement campaigns and individual recommendations is moderate users who have a sufficient but not the highest possible level of engagement. Flash promotions and time-bound offers can best be used to target the satisfied buyers who are motivated to buy due to the discount (Mandung, F., 2024). The reactivation campaigns and personalised outreach are to be carried out on low-value disengaged customers to reconnect them with the brand and remind them why it is important. Lapsed members are those members who continue to be in membership, yet have low satisfaction and buying behaviour, where service recovery initiatives need to be involved, along with the offer of exclusive member offers. This useful framework ensures the connection between technical analysis and strategic decision-making by showing that machine learning can be implemented in marketing management (Lessmann et al., 2021).

The study shows that integrating behavioural clustering and emotional text analysis provides a deeper, more responsive understanding of consumers. The results confirm both academic validity and practical usefulness of ML-based segmentation in the Bangladeshi digital market. The enriched model enables businesses to move beyond traditional models towards targeted, empathetic and data-driven marketing.

5. Conclusion

5.1 Theoretical Contributions

This study aimed to explore the effectiveness of machine learning in improving customer segmentation strategies in the context of the Bangladeshi e-commerce market (Wedel & Kannan, 2016). It was

accomplished through clustering and classification algorithms, sentiment analysis and emotion analysis on consumer review data.

Theoretically, the research confirmed that machine learning algorithms are more effective than traditional demographic-based approaches for consumer segmentation using the application and comparison of the K-means clustering, Decision Tree and Random Forest algorithms (Loh Rahim et al., 2018). There was high accuracy in identifying particular customer segments including loyal customers and low-engagement shoppers. Likewise, the study is relevant for marketing theories as it establishes the most effective characteristics for classifying customers. The strongest attributes that could be used for differentiating various segments were the age, membership status and total spending unlike demographic factors such as gender who had little value in it. This research provides a theoretical validation that ML-based segmentation offers a more prosperous and dynamic understanding of customer behaviour through defining distinct clusters.

Previous segmentation has been based on behavioural and psychographic indicators separately but this study combined them to reveal deeper patterns. As a result, customer actions and emotions explain segment differences and provide a comprehensive theoretical understanding of the decision-making process. The emotional expression in reviews act as a quantifiable psychological indicator that promotes and complements behavioural segmentation. High correlations between sentiment and emotion ratings shows how psychological patterns can enhance the segmentation models and understand customer satisfaction and brand perception (Tan, 2024). This further supports existing theories that combine affective computing and marketing analytics and shows how emotional data can serve as a measurable predictor of customer experience and loyalty in emerging digital economies like Bangladesh.

5.2 Practical Implications

Based on the findings, businesses should focus on behavioural and psychographic techniques and abandon traditional demographic segmentation. Variables like total spend, level of satisfaction and buying frequency provides deeper insight into customer loyalty and profitability than fixed variables.

Segmentation can be simplified by using ML models, especially clustering and classification algorithms like Random Forests, that reveal valuable customer segments and highlight high-risk groups. These models help organisations to identify key behavioural characteristics that are strong predictors of customer value. It supports cost-effective marketing through the minimisation of acquisition cost and focuses more on retaining customers. There are also platform differences that can be presented by the results, as the most important determinants of customer satisfaction are trust and quality of service

(Akinrinoye et al., 2020; Sumit A. Hirve et al., 2024). Targeting initiatives are enhanced with the inclusion of the customer review sentiment and emotion analysis. Emotionally involved consumers in lifestyle and beauty sectors are most likely to be hit through narrative branding, community-based campaigns and influencer marketing (Mandung, F et al., 2024). In contrast, the segments with neutral or negative sentiment should give more focus as they require service recovery or value-communication interventions.

The insights obtained from this study align with the actionable framework presented earlier: loyalty improvement programs for moderate users, flash promotions for discount-driven buyers, and reactivation campaigns for low-value disengaged customers. A strategic machine-learning-driven segmentation model can help companies to optimise the campaign accuracy, retention strategy and dynamically adapt to changing customer expectations.

5.3 Limitations and Future Research Directions

Despite its contributions, this study has some limitations. The use of secondary datasets restricts control over feature design and real-time behavioural capture. Sentiment and emotion detection rely on the quality of textual data, which can be biased or inconsistent. The choice of algorithms used in modelling was also confined to common algorithms.

Future research can address these limitations by using primary data like customer interviews or surveys to help clarify the customers motivation. It is recommended to explore other algorithms such as hybrid or deep-learning models for improving the accuracy. Research may also study the patterns in consumer behaviour and integrate real-time analytics to make segmentation more responsive. Such methodological extensions can enhance the robustness and scalability of ML-based segmentation systems for various industrial and digital platforms in Bangladesh.

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